

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

WITH THE APPLICATION OF SIMPLE PROBLEMS IN THE TEACHING ACTIVITIES OF STUDENTS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

The article shows the urgency of the research on "Management of students' teaching activities in primary school through the application of simple tasks." It is emphasized that the issue should be seen as a task arising from the needs of the student. For the first time, children's perception of task solving as a solution to a vital and practical question, and the perception of the task as a part of life, increase the effectiveness of the learning process.

The content of the article contains theoretical and technological aspects of managing students' learning activities in primary school through the application of simple tasks.

Keywords: teaching activities; task; simple task; solution of the task; condition of the task; the question of the task; solution plan of the task; selection of the action.

Urgency of the research topic. It should be noted that the learning process, students' learning activities are organized and managed through the application of a system of tasks. Prof. A.A. Alizadeh wrote that teaching activity begins with the solution of educational tasks [1; 150-154]. Problems have a special place in the system of tasks, and such tasks are not only informative, but also cognitive and problematic. Students can gain creative experience in the way of the application of the mentioned problems. The selection, systematization and application of the problems aimed at gaining this experience necessitate the identification of areas based on theoretical and technological foundations. The application of the problems is applied at all stages of general education, work in this direction begins with the first lessons of teaching mathematics in primary school. The initial stage is accompanied by students mastering the solution of simple problems. At this stage (in this direction), the level of performance of theoretical and technological-based didactic functions has a determining effect on the educational process at a later stage. Our many years of experience lead us to this conclusion. It is also clear from the analysis of scientific sources that not enough research has been conducted in this direction, and no relevant generalizations have been made. The activities of practical educators also show errors due to theoretical "gaps". Based on the above, we claim the urgency of the research topic.

Interpretation on the research materials. Every teacher who teaches mathematics in a secondary school knows that a child who has just come to school firstly has never heard the words- "a problem", "solution of the problem", "condition of the problem", "question of the problem", "answer of the problem". These terms should be introduced gradually into the students' speech and the teacher should teach them to think about these terms. The issue should be seen as a task born of

children's needs. Children need to see problem solving as a solution to a vital and practical question. "Problems are a part of life, and anyone who can solve a problem can do calculations that happen every minute of life. Such an approach to the problem should be instilled in the brain of the child who is the first to solve the problem. For this, it would be more appropriate for the teacher to give moving questions to the children in the first lessons." [4; 105]

It is known that children first encounter simple problems when watching the actions of a teacher who demonstrates numerical data and actions (it is worth emphasizing here that the answers should be kept secret). For example, the teacher says: "The boy caught three fish (shows cards with pictures of fish) and left them in a bucket (puts the cards in an envelope with a picture of a bucket). "Then the boy caught a fish (shows a card with a picture of the fish) and left it in a bucket (puts the cards in an envelope). How many fish did the boy catch? "

- I told you a task. I repeat it again (repeats the text of the task).

The teacher continues the teaching process as follows:

T. - What do we know? How many perch were there? (There were 3 fish).

T. - What else do we know? How many aspiums were there? (one). We know this, it is clear to us. Everything we know is called a condition.

T. - What do you need to know? What is being asked in the task? (How many fish did the boy catch in total?)

T. - This is the question of the task.

T. - Solving a task means answering its question.

T. - How do you know how many fish there are? Should I plus or minus? Think about it: there were three perches in a bucket, and one aspium was put there, and there were a lot of fish. What to do? Shall we plus or

minus? (it should be plused three fish and a fish).

The teacher writes on the board: $3 + 1$.

After the children say the answer, the teacher writes: 4 is taken.

T. - We wrote the solution of the problem. Did we answer the question? (Yes, we answered). So, we have solved the problem.

T. - Who will answer the question? (Boy caught 4 fish)

After that, it is useful to solve the problem by separating the main elements (condition, question, solution, answer). All this can be asked from one student, and then individual elements of children: Javid says only the condition of the problem, Ayhan says the question of the problem, Rauf reads the solution of the problem, and Shamkhal says the answer to the problem.

Then you can look at the tasks selected by the teacher (from the textbook or various sources) and systematized.

For example, it may be helpful for the teacher to draw the students' attention to the picture. It should be noted that when composing problems on the picture, first of all, it is necessary to teach children to choose numerical data and life events. Which shows the dependence between the quantities. For example, it encourages children to look carefully at a well-chosen picture.

T. - What is drawn here? What was the boy holding? (Flags) How many flags did he hold? What does the girl give him? How many? (One) If a girl gives her flag to a boy, will the boy's flag be more or less? Now what do we know about flags? How can we make the condition of the problem in this picture?

P- The boy had 4 flags. The girl also gave him a flag.

T. - Children, think about what you may ask. Who will find the question in this condition of the task? (If the children have difficulty, the teacher should ask the question himself).

T. - How many flags did the boy have in total?

P. -...

T. - Now repeat the whole task (condition and question together).

P. -...

T. - How will we solve this task? What should be done to answer the question of the task?

P. - It is necessary to plus one flag and four flags, there will be five flags.

T. - Let's write the solution: $4 + 1 = 5$

P. - Who will answer the question? (The boy had only 5 flags).

After saying the answer, it is necessary to "evaluate" it: How many flags did the boy have? (4) How many? (5) After the girl gave him another flag, did he have many flags? Why do you think so? Compare these numbers ($5 > 4$). How big was it?

The process is continued by presenting another task based on the picture (the picture is brought to the screen in front of the students or displayed in front of the board in the appropriate size). It is clear from the analysis of the research materials that this task should be used in this lesson so that it can be developed in this lesson so that it is possible to compare the solutions of

these two tasks.

The teacher should guide the children by asking facilitative questions:

T. - What is drawn here? What was the boy holding? What happened? (one of the balloons explodes) How many balloons did the boy have? Now their number is less, or more?

T. - Children, look at this picture and think, make the condition and the question. Tell me, how will you solve this problem? Answer the question.

It is necessary to write the solution of these two tasks on the board:

$$4 + 1 = 5, 4 - 1 = 3.$$

T.-Why did we plus 1 and 4 in the first task and 1 out of 4 in the second task? (In the first task, the girl gave a flag, there were a lot of flags, in the second task, there were four balloons, one of the balloons exploded, so the balloons were few, so we went out 1).

The main purpose of drawing pictures is to teach children to choose the main elements of the task (condition, question, solution, answer) and to justify (explain) the choice of action to solve it (why did you plus, why did you minus).

Task-solving should always be coordinated with the solution of ready-made tasks suggested by the teacher. Children must learn to listen to the task, to adopt it from the first reading, to investigate without reading again, that is, to analyze it with the new conditions. [7; 306]

On the subject of "numbering" not only the problems of finding the sum and the remainder, but also the problems of increasing and decreasing the numerical (according to the material related to the concept of taught numbers) 1 singularity are solved. [8; 305-310] As a rule, textbooks focus on the system of work aimed at the gradual preparation of children for the solution of such tasks, and such issues are given sufficient attention. Practical work on comparing numbers, increasing and decreasing groups of objects is the beginning of this work. For example, the meaning of the words "increase" and "decrease" is explained with the help of visual aids (1 increased - 1 became more, or in other words, the number of items in the set increased by 1. number decreased by 1). These terms are then reinforced in reading and writing examples. The example of $8 + 1 = 9$ reads as follows: if we add 1 to eight, we get 9, or: if we add 8 by one, we get 9 (the same approach is used in the subtraction work). Then a sufficient number of such tasks are given: "Increase the number 7 by 1: decrease the number 9 by 1, say the name of the number that is one bigger than six, 1 one smaller than eight, and so on. Continuing this process, specific tasks of this type are being resolved. For task: 1) "Draw a piece of fabric 5 cm long, increase its length by 1 cm (decrease): take 7 circles, now make the number of circles 1 more (less)"; or 2) "The boy had to make 3 flags, but one flag made more (less). How many flags did the boy make?"

Such issues are resolved in the usual way. Here, too, the actions required for the solution are selected, as in the case of finding the previously learned sum and residue. Students should conclude that from the context of such an issue, it is clear that in order to find a large

(or small) number, it is necessary to overlap (or subtract).

Thus, at this stage, the main feature of the work on the issues (these issues are specially selected and systematized) is as follows: the task is not repeated as it is read. The repetition of the task is combined with its first analysis - the data and the sought are selected, the numerical data must be memorized by the children from the first reading. This requirement may seem daunting to many teachers at first, but experience (especially the analysis and generalization of research materials we have obtained) shows that if this requirement is met on a regular basis, children can cope and become more attentive. Training to always listen to the problem in this way allows children to concentrate, develop attention, memory, or rather memory.

It is sometimes helpful to suggest that the issue be read "in roles" when dealing with both ready-made and picture-based or observation-based issues. One student plays the role of a condition, the second plays the role of a question, the third plays the role of a solution, the fourth plays the role of an answer, and finally the fifth plays the role of a test. The last stage - the inspection determines whether the question is answered.

It is also useful to use the "price" mentioned above.

The final stage of teaching children to solve problems is of great importance. It is known that in many cases, mistakes in the solution of the problem occur due to the inability of children to relate the answer to the questions they will solve, to think about the accuracy of the answer to the question. Regular application of this requirement is also useful from an educational point of view. Thus, this work helps to instill in children self-examination and critical thinking.

Another important feature of the proposed methodology for teaching task solving is that the actions in task solving are determined on the basis of evaluating quantitative changes in life events described in the text of the problem. Such an approach practically allows to find with confidence the choice of actions (addition or subtraction) on the issues of finding the sum and remainder considered in the "Numbering", increasing and decreasing the number by 1. This is true later, but we do not need to talk about it. (See: [6; 17-21])

Another feature of the case study is that the names of the quantities are not written when solving the problem. Writing a solution to the problem is no different from the task. This is due to the fact that later children will learn to denote an unknown number by the letter "ks", (x) and write the solution of the problem using a numerical formula, and in the numerical formula it is impossible to write the name of any quantity. With this in mind, children need to be taught from the outset to write the solution of the problem in anonymous numbers. Our observations, experiments and observations in scientific sources show that if a teacher regularly and especially carefully checks children's understanding of the meaning of numbers and actions they write, the omission of quantities in problem solving does not affect children's conscious

performance of actions.

The solution of a simple problem is divided into the following moments:

1. Tell the students the condition of the problem.
2. Repetition of the issue with the help of questions and without questions.
3. Identify the question of the issue ("What is being asked in the issue?").
4. Solution: selection of operations and calculations.
5. Expression of the answer to the question.
6. Writing a problem solution. [4; 110-111]

Let's give a brief explanation of each of these moments.

It is better to tell a story than to read a book: children understand the story better than what is read. The teacher clearly states the condition of the problem without haste, with a special emphasis on numerical data. As a rule, it is not necessary to write the given numbers on the board, because the problem is usually given two numbers, and students can memorize these numbers without any difficulty.

The issue is repeated through questions. In addition to being easy to understand, the questions are intended to help students better understand the structure and content of the problem (condition, question). As a result, one or two students repeat the problem without auxiliary questions [5; 68-69]. Images are used in the repetition of many issues. The pictures are intended to better understand the content of the issue, to force children's intellectual activity to work more vividly. To do this, use a variety of media: paintings, pictures, posters, etc. is used.

After the problem is repeated, the teacher once again draws the students' attention to the question (M. - so, what is asked in the problem?). The question is the main part of the problem: this question determines the direction of the student's mental activity (cognitive or intellectual activity): therefore, students must be able to specifically imagine the question of the problem.

When solving simple problems, the process of analysis and synthesis of thinking in students emerges in the simplest way: the question arises from the known of the problem, the known are needed to solve the problem. All of this is given ready-made. The student must choose an action that can solve the problem. Choosing an action is the most difficult and at the same time the main task in solving simple problems. The difficulty is that children do not need to choose an action because the numbers are small. They find the answer based on their information about the composition of the first decimal places. [7; 92-101]

It is necessary to use visual aids on a scientific and pedagogical basis to teach the student to choose an action and to facilitate the mastery of the circumstances in which each action is performed. "Accessibility" should be provided for each student in solving the task.

Suppose such a problem is solved: "It is known that Javid has 7 roots. He gave the rabbits 4 carrots in the morning and the rest of the carrots in the afternoon, and how many carrots did Javid give to the rabbits in the afternoon?"

Holding his face to the students, the teacher says,

"Show with objects that Javid has 7 roots."

Using didactic materials, students distinguish 7 singles (stick, circle, matchstick, etc.). Then the teacher asks again: "What did Javid do to these carrots?" (He gave the rabbits 4 carrots in the morning). What to do with these four roots? (You need to get them out of the 7 roots). The teacher says, "Get out." Students count to 4. "How many carrots does Javid have left?" (3 roots). So, "How many carrots did Javid give to the rabbits during the day?" (Javid gave the rabbits 3 roots during the day).

- The teacher says: "Repeat the whole problem". The student called by the teacher repeats. "Now tell me, how did we solve the problem?" How did we know that Javid gave 3 roots to rabbits during the day? " (We got 4 out of 7, 3 left).

If students have difficulty answering this question, the teacher should help them (facilitation is the teacher's responsibility) and state the answer correctly: "Out of 7 roots, 4 roots should be taken out."

Starting from about the second or third week of the process of teaching this type of problem in primary school, it is useful to ask the student the following question after the problem has been solved: "How did you solve the problem?"

This question can be changed to other options: "What did you do to find the answer?" Or, "How did you find the response?" Later, in some questions, "Why?" you also need to ask the question. This applies to the problem of increasing the number several times and several singles, decrease several singles several and times .

For example, a teacher asks students: "A pen costs 8 copecks and a notebook costs 2 kopecks. How much is a notebook?"

It is advisable to use such a style of work in solving some of these problems. The teacher calls a student and asks him three questions in a row:

1) "How much is a notebook?" (The book is 10 kopecks)

2) "How did you know that the notebook is 10 kopecks?" (I came with 2 cents on top of 8 cents, I got 10 cents)

3) "Why did you come 2 top of 8?" (Because the task says that the notebook costs 2 kopecks).

The problem is written on the board and in the students' notebooks. Writing a solution helps to better understand the use of this or that action in solving this problem. [3; 200-212]

The question is: should I write their names next to the numbers? When students are illiterate or semi-literate (first semester), their names are written next to the problem-solving components.

Writing names makes the writing of the task more visual. When numbers are anonymous, the writing becomes abstract, weakly revealing the nature and process of the student's thinking. But in fact, the child's thinking is figurative and concrete. Accordingly, the writing should be figurative and concrete. Therefore, in the lower stages of training, the names should be written next to the numbers.

Names should be short. Students need to be constantly accustomed to this, because the knowledge

that children receive in their mother tongue does not provide this habit.

There are also some difficult cases of writing, in which case the teacher's help is always needed. Let's note these cases.

1. As is well known, those collected must have the same name, but in the context of the matter, there are often those with different names. In such cases, different types of names should be replaced with common gender names.

For example: "A boy caught 8 carps and 3 bream. How many fish did this boy catch? "

In this case, it is a sexual for carp and breams is a fish. The operation is written as follows: 8 fish + 3 fish = 11 fish. For the names "boy" and "girl", the sexual meaning is "child"; The sexual meaning for the names "male" and "female" is "child": the general term for "apple" and "pear" is "fruit" and so on.

2. The task of spelling names is difficult to solve in the case of increasing or decreasing several singular numbers.

3. It is necessary to use the same notation when increasing the number several times.

Let's write the solution of the following problem: "There are 4 men in one brigade, twice as many women. How many woman works in the brigade? "

There can be two types of writings :

1) $4 \times 2 = 8$ (female) 2) $4 \text{ ad. } \times 2 = 8 \text{ ad.}$ (female)

We reiterate that the teacher is always required to instruct and assist students in writing the names of the numbers.

A good way for students to create their own problem is to test their understanding of the structure of each type of problem individually. Problem-solving should be seen as one of the ways to teach students to solve problems. [2; 613-615]

When constructing a "own" problem, the student has to think more deeply about the relationship between the quantities he has to use for it, he has to choose two quantities that are the basis for finding a quantity, and he has to say that quantity when expressing the question. In short, the student has done a complex job through analysis and synthesis.

It is advisable to give the task of building "similar" issues in the past. In other words, it would be helpful for the teacher to call, "Each of you create an issue similar to the ones we have just resolved with you."

Students can then be asked to create a problem related to this or that activity (for example: 5-3 or 6-2 and so on).

T. - Create a problem that requires you to add 5 to 3 (or subtract 2 from 6).

It is useful to include such tasks in the real process (for this you can give not only anonymous (abstract) numbers, but also named numbers). For example, it is possible to suggest the following task: "Set up a task where 4 cents on top of 6 cents. need to come", or "it is necessary to go from 8 kg to 3 kg".

It should be noted that it is necessary to give convenient constructed problems to the whole class to solve. Possible errors and omissions (such errors often occur in the selection of numbers) should be corrected on the spot.

Scientific novelty of the research. Theoretical and technological directions of management of students' educational activity by application of simple problems in the process of teaching mathematics in primary school have been identified.

Practical importance of the research work. We hope that Determining the theoretical and technological directions of managing students' learning activities in the process of teaching mathematics in primary school with the application of simple problems will have a positive impact on the formation of an environment that includes the elimination of shortcomings in the management of this process.

The result. Determining the theoretical and technological directions of managing students' learning activities through the application of simple problems in the process of teaching mathematics in primary school has a positive effect on the effectiveness of training and provides a basis for the application of the problem system in the later stages.

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